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COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF BIOFUELS AND OTHER ALTERNATIVE FUELS FOR INTRODUCTION IN AVIATION AND WATERBORNE TRANSPORT OF UKRAINE

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Abstract

The purpose of the article is to determine the most promising biofuels and other alternative fuels for Ukraine's aviation and waterborne transport taking into consideration a variety of objective factors and local conditions. Today, aviation's contribution to the global anthropogenic CO₂ emissions is about 1 billion t/year, however with further development of the sector, it may double or even triple by 2050 if no appropriate measures are taken. The most effective GHG mitigation measure is now considered to be the introduction of alternative low-carbon fuels, in particular jet biofuels. Concerning renewable aviation fuels, the term "sustainable aviation fuel" is mostly used. These fuels include synthetic aviation fuel obtained by Power-to-Liquid technology and certain advanced biofuels (synthetic paraffinic kerosene). Shipping currently accounts for about 3% of the global anthropogenic GHG emissions as well as for 15% of the global SO_x emission and 13% of NO_x emission. Alternative fuels for waterborne transport may be numerous including different biofuels, liquefied natural gas, liquefied or compressed biomethane, methanol, ammonia, and hydrogen. The use of renewable fuels in the aviation and waterborne transport sectors is a promising direction of general decarbonization and improvement of the ecological compatibility of Ukraine's transport sector.

Keywords: biofuels, alternative fuel, sustainable aviation fuel, biodiesel, biomethane.

Introduction.

Reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions to mitigate the effects of climate change is one of today's global challenges. The transport sector is responsible for 20% of the total anthropogenic CO₂ emissions in the world. At the same time, compared to other sectors of the world economy, transport is difficult to decarbonize. This especially applies to aviation and waterborne transport where, unlike road transport, there are rather limited opportunities for electrification. Today, aviation's contribution to the global anthropogenic CO₂ emissions is up to 2.5% (about 1 billion t/year), but with further development of the sector, it may increase to 22% in 2050 if appropriate measures are not taken. About 80% of aviation CO₂ emissions occur on flights over 1,500 km, for which there are practically no alternative means of transportation (Doliente 2020). The most effective GHG mitigation measure is now considered to be the introduction of alternative low-carbon fuels.

Regarding renewable aviation fuels, international experts mostly use the term "sustainable aviation fuel" (SAF). At the moment there is no unified definition of the term, though several more or less similar definitions do exist. According to the International Air Transport Association, SAF has three key features: its production is sustainable, which means it neither violates the ecological balance nor exhausts natural resources; it is produced from raw materials that are an alternative to crude oil; it has jet fuel properties that meet technical and certification requirements for the use in commercial aircraft. The International Civil Aviation Organization considers SAFs to be "drop-in fuels" produced

from renewable raw materials or waste that meet the following sustainability criteria: reducing GHG emissions during the life cycle of fuel by at least 10% as compared to petroleum jet fuel and not using biomass from lands with a high carbon stock as raw material for the fuel production (Prussi 2021). In the EU, SAFs are referred to the certain types of "drop-in fuels" that meet sustainability criteria and the requirements for reducing GHG emissions according to the EU RED II Directive. These fuels include synthetic aviation fuel obtained by converting electricity into liquid (PtL technology); advanced (II-generation) biofuel obtained from lignocellulosic raw materials and certain types of waste; advanced (III-generation) biofuel obtained from algae; biofuel produced from raw materials with "high sustainability potential" such as used cooking oil and certain types of animal fats.

From the above, it can be seen that the European Commission does not consider I-generation biofuels, i.e. those obtained from crops intended for food and feed production, to be SAF. In most cases, such biofuels do not meet the requirements for reducing GHG emissions according to the EU RED II Directive: at least 50%, 60%, and 65% for transport biofuel production units that started operation on or before 05.10.2015, between 06.10.2015 and 31.12.2020, and from 01.01.2021, respectively. European Commission's approach to SAF definition seems to be the most reasonable except for the too strict requirements for GHG emission reduction, which may be unachievable now for Ukraine. In addition to SAF, alternative aviation fuels can also include electricity and hydrogen, which depending on their origin may be also renewable

Shipping currently accounts for about 3% of the global anthropogenic GHG emissions. In addition, this sector is responsible for 15% of global SO_x emissions and 13% of NO_x emissions annually. It is predicted that without the introduction of some decisive actions, GHG emissions from shipping will continue growing and could reach up to 130% of the 2008 emission level by 2050, which corresponds to nearly 1.4 billion t CO₂/year. (World Bank 2021). The International Maritime Organization is developing policies to reduce GHG emissions for international shipping by increasing the energy efficiency of ships, as well as introducing new technologies and fuels with low or zero carbon content. The available GHG mitigation measures range from easily achievable operational ones to capital-intensive technical solutions. At that, newly built vessels are expected to have more available options than ships in operation. Existing approaches to decarbonizing international shipping are numerous with the use of alternative fuels and renewable energy having the biggest potential and positive effect (DNV 2021).

Alternative fuels for waterborne transport may be numerous, for example, different biofuels, liquefied natural gas (LNG), liquefied or compressed biomethane, methanol, ammonia, and hydrogen. All the alternative fuels for shipping face some challenges and barriers to their uptake, though the severity of each obstacle varies between fuel types. Typical key barriers include the cost of the required machinery and fuel storage on vessel board, additional storage space demand, low technical maturity of the fuel production technologies, high fuel price, limited availability of the fuel, and lack of the global bunkering infrastructure. Currently, ships can already operate on such alternative fuels as LNG, liquefied petroleum gas (LPG), methanol, and some biofuels. In addition, tests of ammonia and hydrogen as fuels for waterborne transport are ongoing. Among the applications of various types of alternative fuel, it is always important to distinguish between short-distance and deep-sea marine shipping. In short-distance transportation, vessels usually operate in limited geographical areas on relatively short routes with frequent port calls. Because of their relatively low energy requirements, these vessels are often ideal candidates for testing new fuels characterized by high energy conversion or storage costs.

Methodology.

Reduction of GHG emissions in aviation and waterborne transport by shifting to alternative fuels is very topical for Ukraine. Therefore, the purpose of this article is to determine the most promising renewable fuels for these sectors of the country's transport taking into account many objective factors and local conditions such as:

- Level of the technology development and its complexity.
- Experience in relevant areas in Ukraine.
- Competitiveness with traditional fuels by the production costs.
- Reduction of GHG emissions during the fuel life cycle.
- Availability/accessibility of raw material and resource base.

- Technology certification according to ASTM D7566 standard (for SAFs);
- Permissible percentage of mixing with petroleum jet fuel (for SAFs);
- Yield of jet fuel compared to the volume of other co-products (for SAFs from biomass).
- The need to change the aircraft's fuel system and airport infrastructure.
- Compatibility with existing vessel engines/ infrastructure.
- Volumetric energy content of fuels and energy carriers for waterborne transport.
- Standardization of alternative fuels for waterborne transport.

For the aviation sector, sustainable aviation fuels (biofuels, synthetic fuel) as well as the application of electricity and hydrogen have been comprehensively considered. For waterborne transport, such alternative fuels (energy carriers) as LNG, methanol, ammonia, hydrogen, electricity, and different types of biofuels have been assessed and analysed. The summary rating was determined for all the alternative fuels taking into account both, the current and future ratings with a focus on the medium-term perspective (up to 10-15 years). In the long-term perspective (more than 20 years), the situation may change significantly due to the development of modern technologies, alterations in economic conditions, and some other factors. This will have an impact on the priority of the alternative fuels and energy carriers for Ukraine's aviation and waterborne transport, and, first of all, might concern the introduction of "green" power and hydrogen.

Main part

Among the various options for the use of alternative fuels in aviation, in the medium term, the increasing production and consumption of SAFs (in particular, biofuels) as a substitute for traditional jet fuels is considered by experts the most realistic measure from a technical and economic point of view to reduce GHG emissions in the sector. It is expected that only SAFs as alternative fuels will provide long- and medium-distance flights until 2050, short-distance flights until 2040 (then electricity or hydrogen burning will join), regional flights until 2030 (then electricity or hydrogen fuel cells will join), and suburban flights until 2025 (then electricity will join). After 2050, the use of some hydrogen might be technically possible also for medium-haul flights.

Alternative low-/carbon-free energy carriers for aviation could potentially be electricity and hydrogen. However, liquid "green" hydrogen is currently much more expensive than aviation kerosene, and a significant reduction in its cost is predicted by experts only after 2030. Research and demonstration of the possibilities of electrification of the aviation sector are still at an early stage, so this direction will make some tangible contribution to decarbonization rather in the long term (Schwab 2021).

Alternative synthetic fuel for aviation can be obtained by electrolysis of water using electricity, in particular, "green" power (PtL – Power to Liquid technology). However, today, PtL technology is much more expensive than the technologies for the production of

aviation biofuels, and its significant price reduction is expected only after 2030. (Van Dyk 2021). In addition, a key sustainability issue for PtL technology is access to the required amount of renewable electricity due to possible competition from other areas of its use. As a result, in the medium-term future, biofuels appear to be a more promising type of SAF than fuels obtained by converting power into liquid. At the same time, there is an expert opinion that after 2040, the production of synthetic PtL fuel in the EU will prevail over biomass-based SAF due to limited raw materials for the latter (Hughes 2022).

The main advantages of SAF are the possibility of mixing with traditional jet fuel and the absence of the need for changes in the aircraft fuel system and airport infrastructure. The main disadvantage is the limited reduction of emissions other than CO₂ (for example, NO_x, water vapour). For biofuels, there is also a potential problem of limited raw resources in the future with a significant increase in production capacity. As for

electric batteries and hydrogen, the main advantage of their use is a significant reduction of the overall negative impact on the climate during aircraft flight (emissions of CO₂, NO_x, water vapour, condensation trail), the disadvantage being the need for significant changes to the airport infrastructure.

Summary results of the comparative analysis of individual SAFs and other alternative energy sources with an assessment of their rating for Ukraine's conditions are presented in Table 1. For today and the near future the following SAFs are considered the most promising for Ukraine:

- Synthesized paraffinic kerosene from hydro-processed esters and fatty acids (HEFA-SPK).
- Alcohol to jet synthetic paraffinic kerosene (ATJ-SPK) (currently, only conversion of ethanol).
- Fischer-Tropsch hydroprocessed synthesized paraffinic kerosene (FT-SPK).

Table 1.

Comparative analysis and rating of SAFs, electricity, and hydrogen for use in aviation (the summary results).

Fuel	Criteria for evaluating fuels (technologies)						Rating (max 10)
	Attaining commercial level / Experience in Ukraine	Certification / Cost competitive-ness	Blending ratio with petroleum jet fuel / Yield as compared with co-products	High enough reduction of GHG emission	Access to sustainable feedstock/ resources	No changes in the aircraft fuel system and airport infrastructure	
HEFA-SPK	+ / +	+ / +	+ / ±	±	±	+	9
ATJ-SPK	- / -	+ / +	+ / +	+	+	+	8
FT-SPK	± / -	+ / +	+ / ±	+	+	+	7
FT-SPK/A	- / -	+ / -	+ / ±	+	+	+	7
CH-SK	- / -	+ / -	+ / -	-	-	+	6
HC-HEFA-SPK	- / -	+ / -	- / -	-	+	+	6
Co-processing bio-oils in petroleum refinery	- / -	+ / -	-	-	±	+	5
Co-processing synthetic crude oil in petroleum refinery	- / -	+ / -	-	-	+	+	5
HDCJ	- / ±	- / +	-	+	+	+	4
PtL	- / -	± / -		+	±	+	4
Hydrogen	- / -	- / -		+	±	-	4
HFS-SIP	- / -	+ / -	- / +	-	+	-	3
Electric power	- / -	- / ±		+	±	-	2

* When the amount of bio-oils (esters, fatty acids) and synthetic crude oil (Fischer-Tropsch hydrocarbons) used in petroleum refinery for co-processing is <5% (by volume), the obtained aviation fuel meets the quality standards of traditional jet fuel according to ASTM D1655.

SPK/A – synthetic paraffinic kerosene with aromatics, CH-SK – catalytic hydrothermolysis synthesized kerosene, HC-HEFA-SPK – synthesized paraffinic kerosene from hydrocarbon-hydroprocessed esters and fatty acids.

The International certification and classification society DNV identified LNG, LPG, methanol, biofuel, and hydrogen as the most promising alternative fuels for shipping (DNV 2019). In addition, among new technologies, battery, fuel cell, and wind propulsion systems have quite a good potential for application on

ships. Fuel cell systems for ships are under development, and it will take some time for them to reach a degree of maturity sufficient to replace existing main engines. Battery systems are already in use, but on most marine vessels their role is limited by the level of efficiency and flexibility. Batteries cannot store the vast amounts of energy needed to power a large ship (Figure

1). Wind propulsion, while not a new technology, will require some development to make a significant difference to modern vessels. Key factors in the adoption of alternative fuels for waterborne transport are related to

international regulations, environmental benefits, bunkering costs, compatibility with other fuels as well as the availability of required volumes of the fuels.

Figure 1.

Comparison of a volume unit energy content of different fuels with marine diesel oil (assumed as 100%).

According to expert opinion (Grosso 2021), an optimal mix of different types of alternative fuels for decarbonizing marine shipping has not yet been determined. There are potential sustainability, infrastructure, and distribution gaps associated with, in particular, bio-fuels, biomethane, ammonia, hydrogen, and methanol. Investigating the advantages and disadvantages of different alternative fuels for different types of marine shipping would be useful to support increased production as well as their use in marine engines.

In the short term, alternative low-carbon fossil fuels such as LNG, LPG, and compressed natural gas are proposed for achieving rapid reductions in shipping pollution, however, their contribution to decarbonization is limited depending on engine type and methane emissions. The use of battery technology for waterborne transport is considered promising for short-distance transportation. In the future, with the development of this technology, in particular, regarding an increase in charging speed, energy density, and decrease in cost, it will be possible to use battery systems for other areas of shipping.

The specificity of Ukraine's waterborne transport sector is connected with the existing practice of river and sea navigation. Biofuels that replace traditional fuel oil and diesel fuel can be introduced in sea transportation, which allows the use of existing infrastructure and therefore does not require significant investments. But

many different companies and ship owners are operating in the shipping market, including those with foreign registrations, so stakeholders are focused on the global bunkering trends in terms of fuel and emissions requirements. Companies offering bunkering services in Ukraine need to adapt to the global trends, in particular, the development of LNG, ammonia, methanol, and hydrogen applications. On small vessels with gasoline engines, it is possible to use mixed fuels based on gasoline with the addition of ethanol, methanol, and LPG. The introduction of alternative fuels, such as LNG, ammonia, methanol, hydrogen, and batteries for waterborne transport, requires significant investments in supply, storage, and bunkering infrastructure, in charging stations as well as in new vessels or modernization of existing vessels.

Based on the results of the comparative analysis and assessment (Table 2), the following alternative fuels are considered the most promising for waterborne transport in Ukraine:

- Biomethane can be used in compressed (Bio-CNG) or liquefied form (Bio-LNG).
- Biodiesel (FAME) and hydrotreated vegetable oil (HVO).
- Electric power installations with accumulator batteries.
- Liquefied natural gas (LNG).

Table 2.

Comparative analysis and rating of alternative fuels for waterborne transport (the summary results).

Fuel	Feedstock	Criteria for evaluating fuels (technologies)							Rating (max 10)
		Attaining commercial level	Compatibility with existing engines/ infrastructure	Availability/ accessibility of feedstock	Fuel energy content	Standardization	Price	Reduction of GHG emission	
Bio-LNG/ Bio-CNG	Biomass	+ / ±	- / ±	+	+	+	+	+	9
FAME	Vegetable oils/UCO	+ / +	± / +	+ / ±	+	+	± / +	± / +	8
HVO	Vegetable oils	+ / -	+ / +	+	+	+	±	±	8
	UCO and animal fats	+ / -	+ / +	±	+	+	+	+	8
Electricity		+ / -	- / ±	±	-	+	±	+	8
LNG	Natural gas	+ / -	- / -	+	+	+	±	-	7*
FT diesel	Biomass	- / -	+ / +	+	+	+	±	+	6
Green methanol	Biomass	+ / -	- / -	+	±	+	+	+	6
Green ammonia	Biomass	+ / -	- / -	+	±	-	-	+	6
	Water	+ / -	- / -	+	±	-	-	+	6
Green hydrogen	Biomass	+ / -	- / -	+	-	-	-	+	6
	Water	+ / -	- / -	+	-	-	-	+	6
Bioethanol	Sugar/starch-based	+ / +	- / +	+	±	+	+	±	5
	Ligno-cellulose	+ / -	- / +	+	±	+	±	+	5
Dimethyl ether	Biomass	- / -	- / -	+	±	-	±	+	5
HTL bio-oil	Biomass	- / -	+ / +	+	+	-	±	+	5
LPG	Propane/ butane	+ / +	± / -	±	±	±	+	-	5
Straight vegetable oil	Vegetable oils	+ / ±	± / ±	+	+	-	±	±	4
Pyrolysis bio-oil	Biomass	- / -	± / ±	+	±	-	±	+	3
Hydrogen	Natural gas	+ / -	- / -	+	-	-	-	-	3
Methanol	Natural gas	+ / -	- / -	+	±	+	+	-	3
Ammonia	Natural gas	+ / ±	- / -	+	±	-	-	-	3

* It is taken into account that LNG is considered a global transitional fuel on the pathway to zero-carbon shipping.

UCO – used cooking oil, HTL – hydrothermal liquefaction

Findings.

The use of renewable fuels in the aviation and waterborne transport sectors is a promising direction of general decarbonization and improvement of the ecological compatibility of Ukraine's transport sector. There is a required raw materials base for the production of each of the biofuels in question in Ukraine that takes into consideration a sustainable approach to the matter (Geletukha 2021). The base includes oil feedstock (oil energy crops), lignocellulosic feedstock (straw of cereal crops and rapeseed, by-products/residues from the production of grain corn and sunflower, woody and herbaceous energy crops), and starch/sugar feedstock (sugar beet molasses, grain of maize and sorghum). To make the final decision for introducing the

production of a certain type of biofuel for Ukraine's aviation and waterborne transport, it is necessary to perform a comprehensive feasibility study and life cycle assessment for them. For the practical implementation of the production and consumption of these biofuels, certain improvements to the existing legislation will be required.

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